

A Survey on Various Candidate Generator Methods for Efficient String Transformation

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Abstract: String Transformation can be formalized such as given an input string; the system generates the k most likely output strings corresponding to the input string. The essential and important step for string transformation is to generate candidates to which the given string s is likely to be transformed. The different approaches and various candidate generator methods for efficient string transformation are discussed in this paper.

Keywords: candidate generation, string transformation, spelling error correction

I. INTRODUCTION

String Transformation can be generally considered as the natural language processing which includes pronunciation generation, spelling error correction, word transliteration, and word stemming, etc. String transformation is also used in query reformulation and query suggestion in web search. It can be employed in the mining of synonyms and database record matching in the area of Data Mining.

A. String Transformation

As many of the below explained methods are online applications, the transformation must be conducted not only accurately but also efficiently.

Spelling error Correction: Given the list of documents or queries, a spell checker implemented can find the potential candidates for a possibly misspelled word by performing a string search and comparison in its dictionary.

Pre-processing/ Data-Cleaning: Similar information's from different sources have always many difficulties. For example, the address line mentioned as "PO Box 14, East Street." and "P.O. Box 14, East St". Mistakes can be also introduced due to irregularities in the data-collection process, due to human errors, and some other causes. For all these reasons, it is essential for data cleaning to identify similar entities within a collection, or all similar pairs of entities around a number of collections.

Query Suggestion: A very recent important application is to provide answers to query results in real-time, as users are typing their query (e.g., a Google search box with a dropdown suggestion menu that updates as users type).

Such interactive-search boxes are very helpful and have shown to be very important in practice, because they limit the number of errors made by users and also reduce the number of query reformulations submitted in order to find the one that will yield satisfying results.

Query Reformulation: Query reformulation in web search is aimed at dealing with the term mismatch problem. For example, if the query is "NYT" and the document only contains "New York Times", then the query and document do not match well and the document will not be ranked high. Query reformulation attempts to transform "NYT" to "New York Times" and thus make a better matching between the query and document. In the task, given a query (a string of words), one needs to generate all similar queries from the original query (strings of words).

B. Candidate Generation

The essential and important step for string transformation is to generate candidates to which the given string S is likely to be transformed. Candidate generation can be used to find the most likely corrections of a misspelled word from the dictionary. In this case, a string of characters is input and the operators represent insertion, deletion, and substitution of characters with or without surrounding characters.

The candidate generator uses a set of transformations to judge the similarity between two objects, so that only the most similar candidate mappings between the sources are generated. The main function of the candidate generator is to produce an initial set of quality candidate mappings. The candidate generator keeps a record of the set of transformations that were applied for each mapping, which is essential for learning the transformation weights, and

also calculates a set of similarity scores, necessary for learning the mapping rules. When comparing objects, the alignment of the attributes is determined by the user.

The values for each attribute are compared individually. Comparing the attributes individually is important in reducing the confusion that can arise when comparing the objects as a whole. Words can overlap between the attribute values. Comparing the attributes individually saves computation and also decreases mapping error by reducing the number of candidate mappings considered. Given the two sets of objects, the candidate generator is responsible for generating the set of candidate mappings by comparing the attribute values of the objects.

II. RELATED WORKS

The work conducted so far on string transformation can be divided into two categories. Some work mainly considered the efficient generation of strings, assuming that the model is given. Other work tried to learn the model with different approaches, such as a generative model, a logistic regression model, and a discriminative model.

A. Generative Models

Generative model is a full probabilistic model of all variables, which can be used, for example, to simulate (i.e. generate) values of any variable in the model.

Examples of generative models include:

- Gaussian mixture model and other types of mixture model
- Hidden Markov model
- Probabilistic context-free grammar
- Naive Bayes
- Averaged one-dependence estimators
- Latent Dirichlet allocation
- Restricted Boltzmann machine

If the observed data are truly sampled from the generative model, then fitting the parameters of the generative model to maximize the data likelihood is a common method. However, since most statistical models are only approximations to the true distribution, if the model's application is to infer about a subset of variables conditional on known values of others, then it can be argued that the approximation makes more assumptions than are necessary to solve the problem at hand. In such cases, it can be more accurate to model the conditional density functions directly using a discriminative model, although application specific details will ultimately dictate which approach is most suitable in any particular case.

B. Discriminative Models

Discriminative model provides a model only for the target variable(s) conditional on the observed variables which allow only sampling of the target variables conditional on the observed quantities. Despite the fact that discriminative models do not need to model the distribution

of the observed variables, they cannot generally express more complex relationships between the observed and target variables.

A discriminative model requires a training set in which each instance (pair of strings) is annotated with a positive or negative label. Even though some existing resources (e.g., inflection table and query log) are available for positive instances, such resources rarely contain negative instances. Therefore, we must generate negative instances that are effective for discriminative training. Various models are used under the discriminative approach.

i) Logistic Regression Model:

Logistic regression measures the relationship between a categorical dependent variable and one or more independent variables, which are continuous, by using probability scores as the predicted values of the dependent variable. Frequently logistic regression is used to refer specifically to the problem in which the dependent variable is binary (either 1 or 0).

Okazaki's [10] method incorporated rules into an L1-regularized logistic regression model and utilized the model for string transformation. Okazaki's model is a discriminative model. Their model is defined as a logistic regression model (classification model) $P(t/s)$, where s and t denote input string and output string respectively, which utilizes all the rules that can convert s to t and it is assumed only one rule can be applied each time.

ii) Log Linear Model

A key advantage of log-linear models is their flexibility. They allow a very rich set of features to be used in a model, arguably much richer representations than the simple estimation techniques.

The goal of log-linear analysis is to determine which model components are necessary to retain in order to best account for the data. Model components are the number of main effects and interactions in the model. For example, if examined the relationship between three variables—variable A, variable B, and variable C—there are seven model components in the saturated model. The three main effects (A, B, C), the three two-way interactions (AB, AC, BC), and the one three-way interaction (ABC) gives the seven model components. The log-linear models can be thought of to be on a continuum with the two extremes being the simplest model and the saturated model. The simplest model is the model where all the expected frequencies are equal. This is true when the variables are not related.

Dreyer's [3] method proposed a log linear model for string transformation, with features representing latent alignments between the input and output strings. Finite-state transducers are employed to generate the candidates.

Wang [1] also proposed a log linear method but in a probabilistic approach. Wang's learning method is based on

maximum likelihood estimation. Thus, the model is trained toward the objective of generating strings with the largest likelihood given input strings. The generation algorithm efficiently performs the top k candidate's generation using top k pruning. It is guaranteed to find the best k candidates without enumerating all the possibilities.

C. n-Gram Based Models

An n-gram is a contiguous sequence of n items from a given sequence of text or speech. The items can be phonemes, syllables, letters, words or base pairs according to the application. The n-grams typically are collected from a text or speech corpus. An n-gram of size 1 is referred to as a "unigram"; size 2 is a "bigram" (or, less commonly, a "digram"); size 3 is a "trigram". Larger sizes are sometimes referred to by the value of n, e.g., "four-gram", "five-gram", and so on.

An n-gram model [2] is a type of probabilistic language model for predicting the next item in such a sequence in the form of a (n - 1) order Markov model. The n-gram models are now widely used in probability, communication theory, computational linguistics (for instance, statistical natural language processing), computational biology (for instance, biological sequence analysis), and data compression. The two core advantages of n-gram models (and algorithms that use them) are relative simplicity and the ability to scale up by simply increasing n value. When used for language modeling, independence assumptions are made so that each word depends only on the last n-1 words. This assumption is important because it massively simplifies the problem of learning the language model from data. In addition, because of the open nature of language, it is common to group words unknown to the language model together.

D. Pruning

Pruning is a technique in machine learning that reduces the size of decision trees by removing sections of the tree that provide little power to classify instances. The dual goal of pruning is reduced complexity of the final classifier as well as better predictive accuracy by the reduction of over fitting and removal of sections of a classifier that may be based on noisy or erroneous data. One of the questions that arise in a decision tree algorithm is the optimal size of the final tree. A tree that is too large risks over fitting the training data and poorly generalizing to new samples. A small tree might not capture important structural information about the sample space. However, it is hard to tell when a tree algorithm should stop because it is impossible to tell if the addition of a single extra node will dramatically decrease error. This problem is known as the horizon effect. A common strategy is to grow the tree until each node contains a small number of instances then use pruning to remove nodes that do not provide additional information.

Pruning should reduce the size of a learning tree without reducing predictive accuracy as measured by a test set or using cross-validation. There are many techniques for tree

pruning that differ in the measurement that is used to optimize performance. Pruning can occur in a top down or bottom up fashion. A top down pruning will traverse nodes and trim sub-trees starting at the root, while a bottom up pruning will start at the leaf nodes.

Wang [1] uses a top k pruning algorithm to generate the optimal top k candidates.

E. Dictionary Trie Matching

Using the dictionary trie, the misspelled word or string is corrected. Sometimes a dictionary is utilized in string transformation in which the output strings must exist in the dictionary, such as spelling error correction, database record matching, and synonym mining. Specifically, the dictionary is indexed in a trie, such that each string in the dictionary corresponds to the path from the root node to a leaf node. When a path (substring) is expanded in candidate generation, it is matched against the trie, and checked for whether the expansions from it are legitimate paths or not. If not, the expansions are discarded and avoided generating unlikely candidates. In other words, candidate generation is guided by the traversal of the trie. Finally, the identified word pairs are aggregated across sessions and discarded the pairs with low frequencies which improves the accuracy and consumes less running time.

Figure 1: An Example for Trie

These are some of the methods and techniques used for the candidate generation. These methods are compared in the below table. The baseline methods such as generative model proposed by Brill and Moore [3] referred to as generative and the logistic regression model (classification model) proposed by Okazaki [10] referred to as logistic. Log linear model proposed by Wang [1] referred to as log linear.

III. COMPARISON OF VARIOUS MODELS AND METHODS FOR CANDIDATE GENERATION

The various models and methods along with the techniques are compared to know their advantages and disadvantages. The comparison is shown in the table given below.

Table 1: Comparison of various Candidate Generator Methods

Sr. No	Methods	Techniques Used	Advantages	Dis-advantages
I	Generative Model			
1	Brill & Moore's method	Improved error model within noisy channel framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Includes contextual substitution rules - Allows all edit operations 	Very simple model for only single word
2	Duan and Hsu's method	Transform based transformation model using trie	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A* search algorithm configured to deal with partial queries - Capable of capturing users spelling behavior 	Does not penalize the untransformed part of the input query
II	Discriminative Models			
3	Logistic Model Okazaki's method	L1-regularized logistic regression model	Substring substitution rules used as features	High execution time and a large training data to be applied one by one.
4	Log Linear Model i) Dreyer's method	Finite-state transducers	Employed with overlapping features over latent alignment sequences.	Offline application
5		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Top k pruning - Dictionary trie matching method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rule index with A-C Tree. - Pruning algorithm generate the optimal top k candidates 	Better pruning technique may improve more efficiency and accuracy
6	CRF-QR Model	Conditional Random Field- Query Refinement	Query refinement tasks in a unified framework which is mutually dependent and addressed at the same time	Prediction minimizes the performance and accuracy
7	n-Gram based Model	Space-Constrained Gram-Based Indexing	Inverted-list compression techniques with a word-aligned integer coding scheme.	Low performance when compared to trie based pruning method

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, different candidate generator models and methods are learnt and compared. Every model has its own pros and cons. Yet a discriminative model can work better than a generative model because it is trained for enhancing accuracy. Thus various models and methods along with the techniques are compared to know their advantages and disadvantages.

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